

FRDN Network day Discovery Round – Preparation of the discovery sessions

Focus of the session

Topic in focus	Human resources
Topic Statement	All researchers are trained “open science” scientists and proper investments have been made in human resources and training
Other topics that are touched upon (at most 2)	Reward and incentives (Open science minded, experience in OS practices), Open access (experience) , Open science (knowledge, experience)

Scenario:

Executive summary describing the session

Making open science a reality will require investment in capacity building and human capital. While there are actually many other actors required to make this cultural change, it is clear that researchers do have a core role. In this session, we will reflect on which skills are critical to advance open science and whether these skills are present today or more capacity building/training is needed. To do so, we provide participants with an [Open Science skills wheel](#) that are grouped by colour according to thematic areas.

In the first 4 iterations, participants are given a sheet with stickers of different colours (yellow and red) and are asked to place the stickers according to how critical they consider this skill for researchers:

- Yellow sticker: nonessential skills that are not required but can be useful or helpful to Open Science.
- Red sticker: critical skills that are strictly needed to contribute to Open Science.

In the last iteration (session 5), we ask participants to focus on those skills who have the most red stickers (the critical skills). They are given blue stickers to indicate where they think more training and capacity building is needed.

Participants are divided into two groups to make the session flow better, but both groups have to do the exact same exercise.

At the end of each session, we compare the two sheets and reflect on the differences. Through guided questions, we also make them think about how close we are/how realistic it is for researchers to acquire those skills, whether additional support is needed, etc. Finally, we invite participants to join the table if they want to discuss this in more depth.

Premises:

- Due to time limitation, the list of skills/competencies is only limited to Open Science and is not comprehensive. The number of roles is not comprehensive either.
- We are not discussing different competence/skills levels or different career stages. It is assumed that, for most skills, the level increases as career advances. The key question is whether that skill is critical or not for open science.
- There are no right or wrong answers.
- The meaning of the stickers needs to be explained:
 - Yellow sticker: nonessential skills that are not required but can be useful or helpful to Open Science.
 - Red sticker: critical skills that are strictly needed to contribute to Open Science.
 - Blue: (only revealed in the last session) where more training or capacity building is needed.

Detailed scenario of the session

Timing	Approach	Facilitator(s)	Materials needed
1-2'	Exercise explanation by host, pointing the most important premises (create script) Divide group (by position -> half left / half right)		Introduction script
2-3'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participants get 1 minute to read the list of competences. 	Host reads them out-loud with them	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Two A0 posters (per session).
3-8'	Session 1-4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The first person on the line chooses a skill and places a yellow or red sticker. - Then, the second person chooses a different skill and does the same. - Once the last person in the row has placed a sticker, we go back to the first one. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Stickers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 300 yellow stickers (3 packs) ○ 300 red stickers (3 packs) ○ 300 blue stickers (3 packs)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Once all skills have at least one sticker, they can place a second sticker in their skill of choice. This will show skills where there is most and least agreement. <p>Session 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The first person on the line chooses a skill and places a blue sticker. - Then, the second person chooses a skill and does the same. It can be the same or another skill. - Once the last person in the row has placed a sticker, we go back to the first one. - This will show skills where there is most and least agreement. 		
8-10'	Check and wrap-up by host, pointing to most remarkable findings		<p>Script with possible questions or remarks</p> <p>E.g. is there any researcher in the group? What is your opinion? Do you think it is too much? Do you feel the need for support and/or training? Is there currently sufficient support and/or training?</p>

Introduction script:

Host separates the group into two and asks them to position themselves in front of the two panels/wheels.

Session 1-4

Welcome to this discovery session on human resources. The dream statement of this topic is that “all researchers are trained open science scientists and proper investments have been made in human resources and training”. So, today, we are going to look at skills. What are critical skills that researchers should have to make open science a reality? In front of you, you can see an Open Science skills wheel. All of these are skills or competence areas in Open Science. It is of course not fully comprehensive due to time limitations.

Each of you has received a set of yellow and red stickers. What we will do: one by one, by turns, each of you will choose a different skill and will place a sticker according to how critical you think the skill is:

- Yellow sticker: nonessential skills that are not required but can be useful or helpful to Open Science.
- Red sticker: critical skills that are strictly needed to contribute to Open Science.

We are not discussing different competence/skills levels or different career stages. It is assumed that, for most skills, the level increases as career advances. The key question is whether this is a critical skill for researchers (red) or not so much (yellow), in order to advance open science.

We will first have a minute to read the skills, they are grouped by theme (for example: rdm, legal and ethical issues, open access...). Once we have read them, each of you will place a sticker. We start from the centre (#closer to the host) to the side, Then the next one, then the next one and so on. Please choose a different skill each time. If you manage to place one sticker in all skills, then you can repeat and place a sticker on a skill that already has one.

There are no right or wrong answers. Just place a sticker following your first thought.

Session 5

Welcome to this discovery session on human resources. The dream statement of this topic is that “all researchers are trained open science scientists and proper investments have been made in human resources and training”. So, today, we are going to look at skills. What are critical skills that researchers should have to make open science a reality? In front of you, you can see an Open Science skills wheel. All of these are skills or competence areas in Open Science. It is of course not fully comprehensive due to time limitations.

In the previous sessions, we have asked participants to look at the wheel and judge which skills were most critical for researchers to make open science a reality.

- They used a yellow sticker: nonessential skills that are not required but can be useful or helpful to Open Science.

- They used a red sticker: critical skills that are strictly needed to contribute to Open Science.

#Read the skills out loud while participants get to see where the most red & yellow stickers are

Now I am asking you to take a look at the results. You can see that your colleagues considered some skills more critical than others. What you have received is a set of blue stickers. Focusing on the most critical skills, I want to ask you to place these stickers to indicate those competencies where you think more training or more capacity building is mostly or more urgently required. We will do it by turns: we start from the center (#closer to host) to the side. The first person chooses a critical skill that needs training and places the blue sticker. Then the next one, then the next one and so on. You can choose the same sticker as your colleagues if you agree with them.

List of skills

Based on: <https://zenodo.org/record/4727592#.ZCbQYXZByUk> Open Science Skills Visualisation

1. Knowledge of Open Science policies
2. Data management planning
3. Data reuse & open data sources
4. Metadata and metadata standards
5. Research reproducibility
6. Linked data
7. Data preservation & archiving
8. FAIR data principles
9. Persistent identifiers (DOI, ORCID, Handle...)
10. Data sharing and publication
11. Repositories for research outputs (article, data...)
12. Open Access routes (green, gold, hybrid)
13. Negotiating with publishers (Rights retention)
14. Research integrity & ethics
15. GDPR
16. Copyright & intellectual property
17. Licensing in the digital environment
18. Bibliometrics, altmetrics & research impact reporting
19. Engaging the public in research